

EVALUATION OF MEDIUM-SIZED LANGUAGE MODELS IN GERMAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Large language models (LLMs) have garnered significant attention, but the definition of “large” lacks clarity. This paper focuses on medium-sized language models (MLMs), defined as having at least six billion parameters but less than 100 billion. The study evaluates MLMs regarding zero-shot generative question answering, which requires models to provide elaborate answers without external document retrieval. The paper introduces an own test dataset and presents results from human evaluation. Results show that combining the best answers from different MLMs yielded an overall correct answer rate of 82.7% which is better than the 60.9% of ChatGPT. The best MLM achieved 71.8% and has 33B parameters, which highlights the importance of using appropriate training data for fine-tuning rather than solely relying on the number of parameters. More fine-grained feedback should be used to further improve the quality of answers. The open source community is quickly closing the gap to the best commercial models.

KEYWORDS

Survey, question answering, language model, benchmark

1. INTRODUCTION

Large language models (LLMs) are subject of many recent publications and get a lot of attention. Despite that, it is not well-defined what „large“ actually means. Whereas the BERT model with 340 Mio parameters was dubbed „large“ by its creators back in 2018 [1], in 2023 it would not be considered a LLM anymore. Later models kept the original naming convention with “small”, “base” and “large” for a while and extended it into XL and XXL to cope with the growing number of parameters. However, since the size grew even more into hundreds of billions of parameters, it became more usual to put a number suffix like 30B to designate a certain size of a model, which is more concise. Despite that, the term LLM is still used a lot in publications, and has some overlap with the term “foundation model”[2], that is defined as “[..] any model that is trained on broad data at scale and can be adapted (e.g., fine-tuned) to a wide range of downstream tasks”. In our work we refer to LLMs if the model has at least 100 billion parameters and works on text only (which excludes multimodal models). Examples for such models include Googles LaMDA [3] with 137B, Open AIs GPT-3 [4] with 175b and Nvidia’s Megatron Turing NLG [5] with 540B parameters.

One of the benefits of such models is that they are extremely versatile multi-task models. Furthermore, their zero-shot and few-shot performance on a large number of tasks is impressive. Since they are pretrained on text-completion mostly, they are also good for “answering open-ended questions in natural language” which is e.g. explicitly mentioned in the documentation of Aleph Alpha’s Luminous.

Although the last two years were dominated by LLMs like PaLM [6] and GPT-4 [7], notable publications show that smaller models can perform nearly equally well in a lot of tasks and are much more manageable for smaller enterprises and research institutions, e.g. Chinchilla [8] with 70b parameters, FLAN T5 [9] with 11b and LLaMA [10] with up to 65b parameters. AlexaTM20B [11] was trained for 15,360 A100 GPU days and outperforms the PaLM 540B model in 1-shot summarization (MLSum de, XSumen) and GPT-3 175B in machine translation (de-en) and Super GLUE results. An 11B parameter model called Unicorn outperforms GPT-3 175B on Common SenseQA 2.0 by fine tuning a pre-trained T5 model on the RAINBOW datasets [12].

This paper therefore concentrates on evaluating **medium-sized language models** (MLMs) which we define as having **at least six billion parameters but less than 100 billion**. Other researchers in the meanwhile call language models still small, even if they have 11b parameters [13]. Although being quite large with 130b parameters, the GLM model should also be mentioned here, since its creators explicitly modelled it with the goal to make it accessible for researchers with less compute power [14].

Because of the increased capabilities of the LLMs, moving the evaluation to more realistic scenarios beyond purely factual answers seems necessary. The respective ML tasks are called long-form question answering [15] which was originally designed to involve document retrieval before answering the question. However, LLMs and to some degree also MLMs should be capable of performing it as closed-book QA [16]. This poses the problem that evaluation of results is difficult due to ambiguity of questions (ibid) and other challenges. Thus, answers of models are hard to evaluate with wide-spread methods like ROUGE [17]. We therefore perform a human evaluation to test model accuracy.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. We first discuss related work, especially other evaluations of language models. Then, we introduce the dataset used for the evaluation before discussing the choice of models for the test. After that, the experimental setup is described, before AI results and a human baseline are outlined. The paper ends with limitations, conclusion and outlook.

2. RELATED WORK

To evaluate the performance of LLMs a plethora of benchmarks and datasets were published, e.g. Natural Questions [18], BIGbench [19] and MMLU [20]. However, they all concentrate on questions that are automatically evaluable, which means they either test using multiple-choice questions, which limits the language generation capabilities of the LLMs to generate a single character, or use measures like ROUGE and BLEU, who are known to have severe limitations regarding their ability to identify correct answers that deviate from the wording of the ground truth [21]. More recently, GPT-4 and other high-end LLMs were used to assess answer quality of other models, but this strategy has its pitfalls and downsides [22].

Results from holistic evaluation of language models (HELM) [23] confirm the assumption of this paper, that well-tuned MLMs can outperform much larger models. The 52b parameter model from Coherence (v20220609) outperforms the 175b parameters models like GPT-3 davinci v1, J1-jumbo v1 and Bloom. The 52b parameter model from Anthropic (v4-s3) performs even better and additionally outperforms OPT-175b and nearly reaches the accuracy of Turing NLG v2 with 530b parameters. However, the performance of MLMs is very different based on their training, esp. fine-tuning data. T0++ for example performs third best in TruthfulQA EM and outperforms all larger models except GPT-3 175B, whereas it is beaten by much smaller models like GPT-J 6B and all of the bigger ones on NarrativeQA closed-book F1. Similary, UL2 20B performs

relatively well in NaturalQuestions closed-book F1 nearly reaching the performance of Bloom 175B, but is beaten by GPT-J 6B and Bloom 175B in Truthful QA EM (although only by a small percentage).

Another important outcome from [23] is, that “automated evaluation was not satisfying” and it is “necessary to conduct human evaluations to better understand language model performance”. This is done in our paper. The goal of this paper is further similar to HELM in the intend to use the same benchmarks on all considered models instead of a sparse evaluation matrix of tests and models. Besides that, the evaluation in this paper has only a small overlap in models considered (e.g., T0pp and T5) and proposes own tests instead of reusing the popular ones. The evaluation of LLMs in [2] does a good job of summarizing developments of the last years but is not concerned with own benchmark results. Mahowald et al. [24] analyze LLMs from a linguistic perspective and differentiate between formal and functional linguistic competences. Based on literature analysis they reach the conclusion that LLMs are highly competent although not perfect in formal linguistic competence but often fail on functional linguistic competence. The examples they state are however kind of artificial (“How to get a sofa onto the roof of a house”) and also overcome by newer models like LamDA or ChatGPT (like the trick question to translate a sentence that includes a new direction), which they hint to in stating that they are only talking about models trained without human reinforcement or instruction tuning (p. 9).

One major improvement in the advancement of LLMs is using instruction tuning [25]. U-PaLM [26] significantly increases zero-shot performance of PaLM with only 0.1% extra compute, by applying the mixture of denoising training objective from UL2 [27] to a pretrained PaLM model. Flan-PaLM[28] further improves on that by using both instruction-tuning and chain-of-thought prompting. The relative improvement is even greater for the 11B parameter T5 XXL model (+26.6%) compared to the 540B parameter PaLM model (+9.3%).

Similarly, Suzgun et al. [29] find that chain-of-thought (CoT) prompting dramatically increases the accuracy of LLMs in hard BIGbench tasks. PaLM, InstructGPT and Codex benefit with at least 12.9% absolute accuracy increase from low 50ies to high 60ies. The highest increase was found for Codex in the algorithmic tasks (+28.5%). However, for smaller model sizes (8B) there was a negative impact using CoT. For extremely hard tasks, CoT prompting helped the model to create emergent capabilities although those tasks seemed to be not affected by model scale and would require complete new architectures. [30] collect a large number of instructions in order to finetune MLMs on diverse -tasks and achieve good results. Similarly, [31] perform finetuning but use an automatically generated dataset to achieve comparable accuracy on the BIG-bench hard subset.

Multi-step reasoning is still challenging for LLMs [32]. One example for advancement in this area is the Self-Taught Reasoner (STaR) introduced by [33], in which a LLM is trained and refined on its own output iteratively. Specifically, with CoT prompting, the model first generates initial rationales. And then, the model is finetuned on rationales that lead to correct answers. As a follow-up to this work [34] show that LLMs are able to self-improve their reasoning abilities without the need for supervised data by leveraging the self-consistency of reasoning. Benchmarks that can be used for testing commonsense reasoning [32] abilities of LLMs include CSQA, StrategyQA and ARC. We refer the reader to Bhargava and Ng (2022)’s survey for more work in this domain. According to [35], LLMs exhibit reasoning patterns similar to those of humans as described in the cognitive literature.

3. DATASET

Our own dataset is self-constructed and takes some inspiration from existing datasets like BigBench, TriviaQA and AmbigQA. The following categories are included.

- **Abstractions** replace one well-known concept with a different one and force the model to answer based on the replacement.
Example: Assume that purple represents a car and red represents a roof. What do you get if you remove the red part from purple?
- **Basic physics** requires some background knowledge and its application to more or less common situations.
Example: If a ball drops from 2 meters height onto the floor and the floor is made of stone and the ball is made of glass. What happens to the ball?
- **Everyday knowledge** is easy for humans to answer, but unlikely to be found in training data.
Example: 10 year old John is going shopping with his grandfather Raymond. Who is more likely to want to buy some cigarettes?
- **Trick questions** are made to fool humans and it is interesting to see whether the AI can be fooled in the same way.
Example: Which weighs more, a pound of silver or a pound of gold?
- **Metaphors** use well-known English sayings or phrases and turn them into a question. It requires recognition of the saying that is presented in a slightly different form and an understanding of the metaphoric meaning
Example: What kind of coals do you need to take coals to Newcastle?
- **Math word puzzles** are known to cause problems for LLMs. We therefore only include a few of them and also combine them with questions that look mathematical but need no calculation for a correct answer.
Example: If Susan is running faster than Joe, but slower than Mike and the three do a 100 meter race, who will win?
- **Relational reasoning** transfers the rule of three to everyday objects and requires to understand similarities and differences.
Example: A house relates to a skyscraper like a flower relates to what?
- **Deductive reasoning** requires to derive conclusions from the premises of the question.
Example: If the flow of time causes the hands of a clock to turn to the right, what happens if time could run backwards?
- **Symbolic reasoning** is a bit similar to abstractions but uses short variable names instead of words that are defined in a different way as replacements.
Example: If x is a boy and X is a man, what is y if Y is a woman?

Often, a (missing) deeper understanding of the model can be seen when comparing the answers to related questions. In the basic physics category, there are several questions regarding balls dropping on the floor and only the height or the ball material is varied. If the answers reflect this variation, the model seems to be able to capture the required understanding. If it always answers “it bounces” no matter whether the ball is made of rubber, steel or glass, it shows that the model did not understand. We also did vary the wording to find out if it makes a difference how questions are asked. The dataset and answers of the models are published on opendata.iisys.de.

4. CHOICE OF MODELS TESTED

The primary source for models to be tested was huggingface. Models were included if they fall in the medium-size category, are pretrained at least in English language (multi-lingual models were included as well) and preferably already finetuned on closed-book question answering or

instruction-tuned in general. However, we also included models without any finetuning. Models that were trained for extractive question answering instead of generative were excluded as well as those that need a document retriever. Models that are not publicly available like PaLM 62B [6] or Chinchilla 70B [8] were excluded as well.

A first round of comparisons was conducted from November 2022 until June 2023. In this phase foundation models like OPT [36] and LLaMA [10] without any fine-tuning were included as well as instruction-tuned models like Alpaca [37]. Furthermore, several versions of T5 [38] were added to study the effect of different finetuning methods and datasets. These include Flan-T5 [28], mT0 [39], T0pp [40] and T5-SSM-TQAO [38]. ChatGPT from OpenAI, which is a fine-tuned version of GPT-3.5 with 175B parameters and the largest GLM model with 130b parameters serve as a reference for truly LLMs.

Models that were explicitly geared towards dialog like Guanaco, HuggingChat, Koala and OpenAssistant¹ were not included in the comparison and are planned for a future analysis with special focus on chatbots.

The latest additions in the first phase were 4 bit models provided by Huggingface user TheBloke that used finetuning in 4bit and therefore allowed much larger models to be finetuned with limited resources like WizardLM 30B and Wizard Vicuna 30B, as well as models published beginning of June 2023 like Luminous Supreme Control, Falcon 40B Instruct and Dromedary 65B. No models with experimental 8k or larger context size were included.

5. EXPERIMENTS

We followed the instructions of the creators of the MLMs, e.g. by using prefixes like “q: “ before and “a: “ after the question, or “please answer the following question:” as instruction. We did not use any prompt-engineering or chain-of-thought prompting. Except the LLM references ChatGPT and Luminous which were used as part of their manufacturers’ cloud offerings, all models were run on an A100 80 GB GPU (or multiple if necessary) on our local server with FP16 precision. To make results more reproducible we set the temperature value to 0.1.

Open-ended questions have the problem, that they cannot be easily evaluated in an automated way. It is not only possible to give the correct answer in an alternative formulation that might not be detected by current evaluation methods like BLEU and ROUGE [41], but there were also answers given by the language models that were correct and surprising to humans so that even advanced methods like BERTscore [42] would not help detecting the correctness. Flan-Alpaca for instance answered “Tempura” to the question “What relates to Japan like pizza relates to Italy?”. The ground truth answer was “Sushi”, but Tempura seems an even better answer since it is also well-known and additionally closer related to pizza than Sushi. Therefore, a manual evaluation of the answers was performed. Initially, the answers were rated per model. Later on, a cross-check per question across models was performed to assure an equal treatment of each model, since human evaluation comes with the risk of subjectivity.

6. AI RESULTS

In initial tests, **BloomZ** was the best model in the 7B parameter range with 35.5% accuracy. It outperforms Alpaca 7B (chavinlo, 33.6%) in our experiments, but only by a small margin (see

¹ <https://huggingface.co/OpenAssistant/oasst-sft-6-llama-30b-xor>
<https://huggingface.co/KBlueLeaf/guanaco-7B-leh>
<https://huggingface.co/TheBloke/koala-13B-HF>

table 1). Alpaca is based on LLaMA 7B and chavinlos model is not improving the already good base performance of LLaMA a lot (32.7%). However, it was unclear whether the replication of Stanford’s Alpaca that is hosted publicly on Huggingface (chavinlo/alpaca-native) is really performing as good as the original. The keyword alpaca produced 605 results on huggingface (2nd of May 2023). Most have no model-card and several did not run with the code we used for testing LLaMA. However, using Wenxiang Jiao’s **Alpaca** 7B repository produced the surprising result that it was performing not only much better than the first Alpaca model tested, but outperformed all other MLMs with 7b parameters up to this date with 46.4% correct answers. How much of an improvement instruction tuning can give is also visible for **GPT-J** and its fine-tuned version GPT-JT. The latter improves the rather bad 17.3% performance of the base model to 28.2%. This is however still worse than the **Dolly** v1 version with 6B parameters, which is also based on GPT-J and scored 31.8%. Instruct GPT-J further pushes this score to 39.1%. Surprisingly, Dolly v2 does not score better than v1 but only 30.0%, although it has twice the number of parameters. Its base model **Pythia** 12B scores 19.1%, which is also worse than expected.

Table 1. Results of models with 7B parameters and less (33.6% avg.)

Name	Accuracy	Name	Accuracy
Alpaca (chavinlo)	33.6%	LLaMA 7B	32.7%
Alpaca (wxjiao)	46.4%	MPT-7B-Instruct	40.9%
BloomZ 7B	37.3%	OpenLLaMA 7B Instruct	31.8%
Dolly v1 6B	31.8%	OpenLLaMA 7B OpenInst.	30.0%
Falcon 7B Instruct	40.0%	OPT 6.7b	18.2%
GPT-J 6b	18.2%	StableLM 7B	11.8%
GPT-JT 6B	28.2%	WizardLM 7B	47.3%
Instruct GPT-J 6B	39.1%	Wombat 7B	44.5%
		Wombat 7B GPT4	40.9%

StableLM performed exceptionally bad for an instruction tuned model with 11.8% correct answers and also stood out from the rest by often stating “As an AI language model, I do not have personal beliefs or opinions.” It also suspected ethical problems where none were visible e.g., the question “A ten-year-old girl and a 30 year old man sit together in a restaurant. Who is more likely to work there?”.

A last minute addition was **Wombat**, another finetuned LLaMA version, but this time with a reinforcement learning approach [43]. It is available in two versions with instructions generated by ChatGPT and GPT-4 respectively. Both perform very good and nearly reach Alpaca’s performance. However, they behave quite differently since the GPT-4 instructed model gives quite concise answers (either right or wrong), whereas the other version produces very verbose answers and starts nearly every answer with “As an AI language model, I do not have personal beliefs or opinions”. With Falcon 7B and MPT-7B, two strong competitors joined the field in June 2023 with 40% and 40.9% correct answers. They both rely on own pretrained models and can therefore be used commercially, in contrast to the LLaMA-based alternatives. Finally, WizardLM took the lead in the 7B parameter models with 47.3% correct answers.

The finetuned **T5** family of models performed rather good in our tests (see table 2). Scores reach from 37.3% to 44.5% of Flan-T5. However, they still perform slightly worse than the smaller models Alpaca 7B and WizardLM 7B. Flan-Alpaca and Vicuna 13B perform similarly good. T5 also shows how much of an effect finetuning has, since the base model scores only 13.6% which means 24% to 30% increase absolute. One notable exception is **mT0** xP3 XXL, which is a multi-lingual version of T5. It seems that its subpar performance with only 20.9%

correct answers is due to the multi-lingual pretraining since BloomZ 7B is also finetuned with xP3 and shows very good results.

Table 2. Results of models with 10B to 13B parameters (35.4% avg.)

Name	Accuracy	Name	Accuracy
Airoboros 13B 4b	46.4%	Cerebras 13B	19.1%
Dolly v2 12B	30.0%	Flan T5 XXL	44.5%
Flan Alpaca XXL	44.5%	GLM 10B	37.3%
GPT Neo X	14.5%	LLaMA 13B	38.2%
mT0 xP3	20.9%	Minotaur 13B fixed	56.4%
Nous Hermes 13B	56.4%	OPT 13B	10.9%
Orca Mini 13B 4b	28.2%	Pythia 12B deduped	19.1%
T5 v1.1 XXL	13.6%	T5 XXL SSM TQAO	37.3%
Vicuna	41.8%	T5-11b-TQAO	38.2%
WizardLM 13B	52.7%	WizardLM 13B 4b	53.6%

Vicuna and Flan-Alpaca tend to give correct, but longer answers on average (93 and 115 characters) compared to the T5 models (~16 characters) and also compared to LLaMA, GLM and BloomZ (between 50 and 15 characters). They are more similar to ChatGPT in this respect (128 characters). **WizardLM** [44] performs very well in 4 bit GPTQ version with 13b parameters from TheBloke (53.6%) and therefore clearly outperforms Flan T5. The direct comparison shows, that the quantization indeed does not decrease performance, since the 4bit model performs even slightly better than the FP16 model. However, WizardLM is beaten in the 13B param category by Nous Hermes and Minotaur, that both are very close to ChatGPT’s performance with 56.4%.

Orca-Mini is a first try to mimic the training strategy of Microsoft’s Orca [45]. However, it is failing miserably and achieves only 28.2% correct answers whereas the original Orca is able to outperform ChatGPT in most tasks and gets even close to GPT-4’s performance.

The **OPT** family of models showed subpar performance with 11% correct answers for the 30B parameter model (see table 3) and seems to prove the warning you often read, that pre-trained models without any finetuning are not usable for downstream tasks. However, if you consider **GLM-10B** and **LLaMA-13B**, the models achieve 37.3% and 38.2% correct answers without any finetuning, the statement doesn’t seem to be correct. They are therefore in the same performance range as T5 finetuned on closed book QA and instruction tuned T0pp with accuracies between 37.3% and 40%. The larger models OPT-30B and LLaMA-30B did not outperform their smaller siblings. OPT-66B was significantly better than the smaller OPT models, but still substandard given its size. OPT-IML 30B and **Galactica** 30B with 18.2% and 12.7% respectively, were also rather disappointing. We could not produce usable results with LLaMA 65B, which may point to an erroneous checkpoint being leaked / published.

The 70B parameter model Luminous Supreme from the German startup Aleph Alpha performs similar to OPT-66B with 30% accuracy. In June, a new version of it called “control” was published that increased this result to 41.8%, which is still below the best 7B parameter models. After the publishing of QLoRA in May 2023 [46], a lot of new instruction-tuned models with 30B parameters and more were published. This pushed the previously low average score of the largest models significantly. However, the gain compared to well-trained smaller models is not large. WizardLM’s performance increases from 53% to 56.4% by increasing the model size from 13B to 30B parameters. MPT jumps from 40.9% (7B) to 48.2% (30B) accuracy. Alpaca even drops from 46.4% (7B) to 45.5% (30B). However, a few other competitive models got available. Falcon 40B instruct achieved 55.5% accuracy, the same as IBM’s **Dromedary** with 65B parameters and

GPTQ [47]. Allen AI’s **Tulu 30B** performed only mediocre with 49.1% compared to Caldera AI’s **Lazarus 30B** that achieved 64% and therefore outperformed ChatGPT (60.9%). The best overall models however came from a single developer called Jon Durbin. His **Airoboros** model outperforms ChatGPT and Lazarus with 65.5% accuracy (65B 4bit model) and even outperforms the human baseline with 71.8% with its 33B parameter model.

Table 3. Results of models with 30B parameters and more (44.8% avg w/o ChatGPT)

Name	Accuracy	Name	Accuracy
OPT 30B	11.8%	LLaMA 30B	33.6%
OPT 66B	30.0%	LLaMA 65B	0% ²
OPT-IML 30B	18.2%	GLM-130B	33.6%
Alpaca 30B 4b	45.5%	Camel 30B comb 4b	58.2%
Dromedary 65B 4b	55.5%	Falcon 40B instruct	55.5%
Galactica 30B	12.7%	MPT-30B instruct	48.2%
Luminous Supreme	30.0%	Lazarus 30B 4b	64.0%
Luminous Supreme Control	41.8%	Airoboros 33B 4b	71.8%
Tulu 30B 4b	49.1%	Airoboros 65B 4b	65.5%
WizardLM 30B 4b	56.4%	ChatGPT 3.5	60.9%
Wizard Vicuna 30B 4b	59.1%	<i>Human baseline</i>	<i>70.1%</i>

7. HUMAN BASELINE

A test with different groups of humans was performed to determine a human baseline per category of questions. This is not only used to compare the performance of MLMs but also to verify the judgement of what a correct or plausible answer should look like. All participants were non-native English speakers but had a good English speaking level so that they can attend English study programs. 32% had a background in computer science, 22% in business administration, another 22% in engineering and the final 22% other. The questions that were asked to the AI models were split into four questionnaires, so that every participant saw only parts of the whole question catalogue which helped keeping the time to answer within bounds (15.5 min median). The participants did not get any incentives for participating.

Overall, there were 87 participants (41.4% female, 54.0% male) who finished the questionnaire (dropout 8.4%). The median age was 23 years (avg. 25.8).

It was expected that humans would in general be able to answer the questions, but would also make a couple of mistakes, so that the baseline would be around 90%. Astonishingly, the average human score was only 70.1%. Questions were partly trivial to answer for humans, but also partly challenging. As expected, a significant portion of humans had problems both in math word questions as well as abstractions and symbolic reasoning. They also fell for some of the trick questions. Some had problems with missing background knowledge especially for historic celebrities like Margaret Thatcher or Edwin Moses due to their young age. Still, some of the subjectively trivial questions like relations between animal types resulted in surprising answers (e.g. donkey and zebra as an answer to “A tiger relates to a wildcat like a horse relates to what?” instead of pony). On the other hand, some of the questions that were rather controversial because they seem underspecified, were answered relatively homogeneously in the expected way. Especially age-related behaviour was only scarcely questioned and over 95% of participants agreed that children are more likely to eat ice cream than their grandparents and vice versa for

² Wetestedthemodelwith a numberof different prompts and hyperparameters, but itkept on repeatingthequestioninsteadofgivinganswers. We also tested different models on huggingface, but all hadthe same issue.

cigarettes. It can be seen as confirmation of prejudice or as a Fermi question, but most respondents agree that females are more likely to buy hair colour than males (87%). Regarding the trick questions there were large differences. Some of the obvious ones were answered worse than expected, e.g. only 26% of respondents noticed, that an electric train does not produce smoke and only 5% found that the car which can drive up to 120 km/h won't accelerate to 200 km/h. On the other hand, only 25% fell for the question about how long bamboo needs to grow to 30m height, if it can grow up to 20m tall, although it is quite similar.

Surprisingly, the wrong answers from humans were the same or very similar to those of the AI models, even if the question did not push them into the wrong direction as it is the case in the trick question category. Both humans and AI e.g., saw the symbols XYxx as an indication of transgender instead of a family with two boys since it was defined in the question that X represents a man and Y a woman.

8. DISCUSSION

On average, the MLMs were able to answer 35.3% of questions correctly, which means just over a third. We therefore conclude that our dataset is challenging. The best performing model was Airoboros 33B which scored 71.8% and therefore clearly above the reference LLM ChatGPT (60.9% correct answers) and even slightly above the human baseline. Some of the larger MLMs, especially the 30B parameter models were somewhat disappointing since they did not outperform their smaller siblings. However, the best models were still from this category. It is also surprising that the correct answers of the models, especially Flan-T5 and Vicuna 13B are somewhat complementary. The 44.5% and 41.8% of the models add up to 62.7% correct answers which even outperforms ChatGPT (60.9%). You would expect that questions are either harder or easier for models to answer and that well performing models give good answers to the same questions, if the questions were not included in their training data. However, across all MLMs the correct answer rate was 91.8% and together with ChatGPT only 4 questions could not be answered correctly.

Short answers are preferable for factual information, while longer answers are suitable for fact-based judgments. The models allow for additional parameters, such as specifying the maximum number of tokens for the answer. However, this often results in truncated answers that abruptly end in the middle of a sentence, rather than providing shorter responses. Ideally, the model should autonomously distinguish between answers that are better when answered concisely and those that require additional explanations. However, there is also a subjective notion to that judgment. An MLM's poor quality is evident when it generates unrelated text or merely reproduces training data without providing a relevant answer. A similarly bad behaviour is **asking new questions** that are almost identical to the original question but do not contribute to a proper answer. It sometimes seemed, as if this was the MLMs way of saying: "I have no idea". The ability to **confess being unknowledgeable** is lacking in all models but GPT Neo X.

Filtering to avoid biases seems rather undesirable. It would be better to train the model for desirable answers. Not only ChatGPT with filtering, but also StableLM and WizardLM without any filtering showed signs of trying to teach the user, e.g. in preaching healthy living styles without smoking when being asked about wildfires that are caused by smokers. This seems also undesirable, although in general giving advice for self-improvement of the user can be considered good. Another similar issue is the answer: "It is not appropriate to make assumptions about a person's personal preferences based on their age." given by StableLM on the question about the likelihood of buying something based on age.

Repeating the question as part of the answer has pros and cons but was considered rather undesirable. Luminous has even an option for penalizing this, although it did not seem necessary there. ChatGPT on the other hand does that very frequently.

Generating options before giving an answer must be viewed as an undesirable feature and is present in many models that are not finetuned. Galactica is one of the worst regarding that. Sometimes models do generate only options with no choice afterwards, or the options were so long, that they did not fit into the maximum answer length. This was rated equally to unanswered or wrong answer.

Hallucination is a well-known problem of LLMs and not surprisingly, the problem was observed for MLMs as well. To go into more detail, a conspicuous situation that seems to force MLMs to hallucinate are questions regarding similarities. This is a situation where humans as well might get into speculating if they do not find an obvious similarity. Since LMs in general do have problems in confessing that they do not know about certain things, it is not surprising, that they invent similarities between the celebrities, e.g. common birthplace, age of dying, art or sport area and so on.

Prompt engineering should only be an intermediate step towards better language models, since it should not be the task of a human to ask the question in a way that allows the LLM to give the correct answer, but the LLM should be trained in a way that allows it to understand all kinds of questions and always gives the best possible answer (given its training data). For Luminous for example, it made a great difference whether it is prompted with the context and question only, or there was a prefix “question: “ before the actual question. It did not help to put the “question: “ prefix before the context. With the prefix, the answers were much better than without. It is even very picky regarding some wordings, e.g. it is more likely to produce correct answers if you start the context with “let’s assume” instead of just “assume”.

Mathematical capabilities of the models tested are very different. Some models are able to perform some basic calculations like adding, subtracting, multiplying and dividing and use these capabilities to solve some simple math word problems. However, in most cases they struggle if there are too many calculations involved, even if they are simple to calculate. They also mostly fail to do unit conversions, e.g. from meters to centimeters or from kilometers per hour to meters per second. Astonishingly, ChatGPT is able to do the latter, but unable to correctly perform the former, although it recognizes that it has to do a conversion.

Regarding **scale**, there was no clear tendency. Although larger models performed better in general (e.g. LLaMA 13b was 5.5% absolute better than LLaMA 7b), both LLaMA and OPT 30b models performed worse than the smaller models. Also, Galactica 30b and OPT-IML 30b were not as good as expected and even the 70B Luminous Supreme model performed worse than several 13b and even 7b parameter models. The assumption is, that the 30B and larger models are **undertrained** compared to the smaller models. This finding is in line with the degradation of LLaMA 65B compared to LLaMA 33B in zero-shot settings for NaturalQuestions, ARC-e and ARC-c [10]. Typically, larger models with enough training outperform smaller models in every aspect and especially in zero-shot performance. We also hypothesize that instruction-tuned models perform better the **more compute was invested in their finetuning**. Another reason could be that for demanding tasks a low score of around 20% accuracy is still in the area where chance plays a role. The empirically observed hockey-stick curves when scaling language models and evaluating their performance compared to scale seems still in the “blade” area of the curve and not yet in the “shaft” area.

Comparing the performance of OPT and LLaMA, the latter models perform way better than OPT, so there is an **advancement from OPT over OPT-IML to LLaMA**. This seems to be due to increased training data and also epochs of training. Meta doesn't state exactly how long the OPT models have been trained, but the usage of 992 A100 GPUs compared to the 2048 for LLaMA together with the increase in training tokens from 180 B (OPT) to 1.4 T for LLaMA suggest that OPT is heavily undertrained and LLaMA compares to OPT similar as Chinchilla [8] compares to Gopher.

9. SECOND EVALUATION ROUND

A second round of evaluations was conducted in December 2023, some additional models have been tested that reflect the latest developments in MLLMs. Compared to the models until June 2023, especially new models with 7B parameters have been analysed regarding their performance. The accuracy of the best model with 7B parameters has increased from 47.3% to 62.2% which is an increase of 31.5% relative and outperforms the ChatGPT 3.5 performance of January 2023. For recent models with 13B parameter models, only **Orca 2 13B** was tested which slightly increased the accuracy of the previous best 13B model from 56.4% to 57.2%. It strengthens the suspicion that further optimization with supervised finetuning seems to plateau and only better foundation models can significantly enhance the performance, as it was done with **Mistral 7B**. In the 30B parameter category, **Yi 34B** was the prominent new entry. It performs on par with the best 7B model and was only marginally worse than the previous second best 30B model (Lazarus 30B with 64%). However, it could not match the performance of the previous best model Airoboros, which might indicate some problems with polluted datasets for Airoboros. A long envisioned new entry in the list of contenders is **Mixtral 8x7B** which is based on the Mixture of Experts architecture [48] and therefore a sparse model like Google PaLM and presumably GPT-4. Despite its good performance with 63.1% it does not outperform previous models like Lazarus 30B or Airoboros 33B and 65B.

Table 4. Results of human evaluation of models from December 2023

Model	Accuracy	Chars	Words	Inf. time	Token/s
DEITA 7B v1.0 (float32)	56.3%	68,130	12,316	0:36:58	10.29
Dolphin 2.2.1 Mistral 7B	62.2%	51,298	9,139	0:03:04	93.36
Dolphin 2.2 Yi 34B	62.2%	32,491	5,955	0:05:04	35.79
Mistral 7B DPO	58.6%	58,454	10,584	0:03:38	89.79
Mistral 7B Instruct v0.2	55.0%	64,001	11,467	0:04:08	86.42
Mixtral 8x7B Instruct v0.1 4bit	63.1%	63,214	11,347	0:12:52	27.42
Neural Chat 7B v3.3 Slerp	59.5%	52,678	9,734	0:03:10	92.85
Orca 2 13B	57.2%	38,007	6,973	0:03:03	69.55
Phi 2 (float16)	39.6%	43,877	7,857	0:06:08	39.93
Solar 10.7B Instruct	56.3%	67,535	11,896	0:06:10	61.13
Starling 7B alpha	56.8%	53,405	9,654	0:03:30	85.16

In table 4, there is data for accuracy of all newly tested models. In addition, speed measures have been collected and calculated. They show, that even within models with the same parameter count, speed differences can be found. Tokens are calculated as 3 characters. The number of characters and words also shows whether models tend to give shorter or longer answers. All tests were again performed on an A100 80GB card. Mixtral, Phi 2 and DEITA were run with the stated precision. All other models use 4bit GPTQ, which is much faster.

10. LLM AS A JUDGE

Recently, the usage of LLMs as a judge for evaluation of language models has become the de facto standard, since it seems to offer a good balance between semantically correct evaluation of answers to open-ended questions and manual effort. Most of the time, GPT-4 is used [49], but lately specialized language models are proposed as alternatives [50], [51], [52]. We included results of automatic evaluation from JudgeLM and Auto-J. They rated model answers against each other, and we calculated an Elo-rating from these results (see Table 5). The correlation between Auto-J and JudgeLM scores is 0.797. Comparing these numbers to the well-known Open LLM leaderboard from Huggingface, we see some significant differences. Although our own evaluation dataset includes some mathematical questions, it is not as math heavy as the inclusion of GSM8k at Huggingface. The biggest advancements in the overall score at Huggingface in the last months mainly came from advances in maths (see Table 6). If you look at Minotaur and Lazarus for example, they perform not too bad in ARC, HellaSwag, MMLU and TruthfulQA in comparison to the top models (~13% and 19% difference absolute), but they lack behind 62% and 58% in GSM8k. Compared to the human evaluation (see Table 4), we see that Yi and Mixtral-based models are again at the top and very close in their performance. DiscoLM German 7b is a notable model, since it is finetuned for German language, but is still one of the best 7b models in English language. Although it cannot be precisely concluded from model results, we argue that some datasets proved to lead to higher quality results, especially Nous Hermes and Dolphin. However, new finetuning methods like direct preference optimization (DPO) [53] and model merging with mergekit³ have also contributed to the current best models.

Table 5. Results of automated evaluation in January 2024

Model	Auto-J	JudgeLM	OpenLLM
Airoboros 33B gpt 41.4	783	817	58.20
Cosmosis 3x34B	1007	1088	75.39
DiscoLM German 7b v1	1015	1041	x
FusionNet 7Bx2 MoE 13B DPO	946	961	77.44
FusionNet7Bx2MoE14B	956	1031	75.91
Lazarus 30B	1024	995	58.4
LeoLM 7b chat bilingual	1107	843	x
Minotaur 13b fixed	917	919	55.19
Nous Hermes 13B GPTQ	883	937	54.02
Nous Hermes 2 Mixtra 18x7B DPO	1191	1153	73.35
Nous Hermes 2Yi 34B	1161	1199	73.74
SOLAR math 2x10.7b v0.2	1130	1141	74.25
WizardLM 7B uncensored	827	793	44.92
Wxjiao Alpaca 7b	858	879	x
Yi 34Bx2 MoE 60B	1094	1107	76.72

³<https://github.com/arcee-ai/mergekit>

Table 6. Result details from Huggingface Leaderboard

Model	ARC	HellaSwag	MMLU	TruthfulQA	GSM8K
Cosmosis-3x34B	69.71	85.18	77.25	63.82	72.25
FusionNet 7Bx2 MoE 13B DPO	74.91	89.30	64.67	78.02	69.52
FusionNet 7Bx2 MoE 14B	73.55	88.84	64.68	69.6	70.66
Lazarus 30B	64.93	84.27	56.47	58.65	7.73
Minotaur 13b fixed	59.04	81.66	50.1	50.36	13.12
NeuralBeagle14-7B	72.95	88.34	64.55	69.93	70.28
Nous-Hermes-2-Mixtral-8x7B-DPO	71.08	87.29	72.17	54.83	71.65
Nous-Hermes-2-Yi-34B	66.89	85.49	76.7	60.37	70.05
SOLAR-math-2x10.7b-v0.2	70.90	88.29	66.25	71.68	64.9
Yi-34Bx2-MoE-60B	71.08	85.23	77.47	66.19	75.51

11. GERMAN MODELS

We finally conducted a comparison of German speaking models on a translated version of the dataset. We made sure to pay attention to translation details like phrases that cannot be translated automatically. So, the English question regarding “taking coals to Newcastle” was translated as “Eulennach Athen tragen” (taking owls to Athens), which is the German equivalent, although very different from a word-by-word translation perspective.

We included models available on Huggingface until January 2024 that were explicitly marked as German, as well as one version of Mixtral and Mistral each, that are known for their pre-training in multiple languages, including German. Some models like EM german 7b v01 did not produce meaningful output and are therefore not listed in Table 7.

In contrast to English models, German 7b models were not able to outperform the bigger ones. The two Mixtral-based models take the lead with 70.8% and 65.8% accuracy respectively. Astonishingly, the model with a German finetuning scored worse than the one without and there was no significant difference in command of German language.

Please note, that these numbers cannot be directly compared to results from June 2023 because of newly added questions with factual character as well as questions regarding bias.

SauerkrautLM 13b secured the third place in the comparison, with a significant gap in accuracy compared to the Mixtral models (50.0%). The two 7B parameter models DiscoLM German and EM German Leo Mistral are close behind with 48.9% accuracy both. DiscoLM was also the fastest German model with 62.4 tokens per second on an A100 80GB. Mixtral models were evaluated in 8 bit due to the lack of GPTQ-based versions, the other models in 4 bit (GPTQ).

We scored questions that were given in English instead of German as wrong, independent of their factual correctness. This was mainly the fact for the bilingual LeoLM, but also for Mistral 7B Instruct. Besides that, we did not pay attention to grammar or spelling mistakes as well as single English words in the German answers, as long as the answer was still understandable. Mostly, accuracy scores also reflect German writing skills of the models except for Mistral 7b instruct. This model scores relatively well despite its bad German skills and had even higher accuracy if we would have included the correct answers given in English.

Table 7. Results of German Model Evaluation

Model	Accuracy	seconds	characters	token/sec
DiscoLM German 7b v1	48.9%	429	80,252	62.4
EM German 13b v01	39.1%	618	82,793	44.7
EM German Leo Mistral	48.9%	384	69,807	60.6
LeoLM hessianai 13b chat	47.5%	684	86,997	42.4
LeoLM hessianai 7b chat	30.3%	495	97,064	65.4
LeoLM hessianai 7b chat bilingual	18.3%	528	128,773	81.3
LeoLM Mistral hessianai 7b	32.0%	612	98,148	53.5
Mistral 7B Instruct v0.2	42.6%	716	94,933	44.2
Nous Hermes 2 Mixtral 8x7B DPO	70.8%	10,544	96,304	3.0
SauerkrautLM 13b v1	50.0%	353	47,338	44.7
SauerkrautLM 7b v1 Mistral	43.7%	238	42,291	59.2
SauerkrautLM Mixtral 8x7B	65.8%	13,445	162,448	4.0

For the factual questions, they were answered much more accurately than the ones that required reasoning, which was expected. For the question that tried to produce a biased answer, most models got the full score with six out of six correct answers. It seems that this has led to overly correct models that shy away from any answer that could be interpreted as politically incorrect. This is especially visible for the question whether Mary or Gary is more likely to be pregnant. Many models do not think, that being a woman results in a higher likelihood of pregnancy compared to a man. Some even argue explicitly that this would be a prejudice. Even explicitly asking for a pure statistical answer did only slightly increase the accuracy over all models. In less obvious form, the same applies to questions about who is more likely to work in a restaurant or school (10 years old or 30 years old) and buying behaviour based on age or gender. While some models offer a statistical perspective and therefore the expected answer, most models argue that without further information about personal preferences it was impossible to give an answer.

12. LIMITATIONS

Inference time was not measured explicitly, but never exceeded a few seconds (<5). per question on an A100, depending on the number of tokens produced (<100) and the model size (<30B). The human evaluation was done by the authors only. For future work, there should be a cross-check with more human evaluators.

Only a small number of test questions was used (110 for the first phase, 142 for the second). This kept the effort for human evaluation within bounds, but as a downside, tests only a limited amount of application areas, e.g., no questions were included that tested for chemical knowledge or like MMLU does.

The human baseline was limited to students and university staff and all were non-native speakers of English language. We did not perform any further analysis of correlations between number of correct answers in a specific question category and the academic background of the participants yet. For German questions, we don't have a human baseline yet.

The evaluation was done with FP16 for all models, initially. Later on, 4bit quantized models were tested using the GPTQ for LLaMA framework. We tested a few models in both FP16 and int4 and could not find a significant difference. Therefore, models available in GPTQ format were used wherever possible since June 2023.

The choice of models was somewhat arbitrary and only roughly guided by OpenLLM results lately, and models coming to our attention at Huggingface as “trending” or new initially.

13. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

If you take together all the right answers from the different MLMs, 91.8% of the questions were answered correctly. The question remaining is therefore, how to combine the best of all models into a single model within a range of 7-30B parameters. It seems that using the **right training data for finetuning** is more important than the pure number of parameters. However, this finding might be due to a similarity of some training data to our own dataset. It was beyond the scope of this paper to make a detailed evaluation of the overlap between questions in our test dataset and the training data of each model tested. We assume that the overlap is rather small, since we took quite some efforts to come up with unique questions. Only the trick questions are likely to be included in training data, since they were taken from the internet. However, performance on those was rather bad. Only one model correctly answered the question about getting out of an imaginary room and only the most recent models were able to figure out, an electric train does not produce smoke.

Results in **German language** are also reasonably well already, although not being as good as the English counterparts, especially for smaller models. While Mixtral-based models perform on par, the 7b parameter models fall short compared to their English counterparts. This is especially true for DiscoLM. Although it is one of the best German models, it performs exceptionally well in English tests, outperforming all 13B models tested. The bilingual LeoLM got an even higher score from Auto-J than DiscoLM for English answers, but produced mainly unusable answers in German language. It is also a notable exception for the congruence of scores from JudgeLM and Auto-J. While the median of the difference between the two scores is 34, for bilingual LeoLM it is 264. Excluding the new factual and bias-related questions and therefore making results better comparable to the older English ones, the performance of the best 7b model in German was only 43.2% compared to 62.2% in English. We conclude that there is significant room for improvement for these German models. We hypothesize that there are not yet as high quality German instruction tuning and DPO-datasets as there are in English language.

Instruction tuning however, also seems to have its limitations. Although it can significantly enhance the performance of base models, it still seems to plateau with a given base model. Only **better foundation models** like Mistral, Starling and Yi can provide the means for a performance boost to a completely new level. Comparison of own test results with popular benchmarks like MMLU, MT-Bench and GSM8K show, that models seem to be optimized for certain type of questions. Starling 7B e.g. outperforms all other 7B and even larger open source models on MT-Bench and MMLU, whereas in our tests it does not reach the performance of Dolphin Mistral 7B or Neural Chat 7B. This is partly due to bad performance on trick questions, but also due to symbolic reasoning.

Instruction-tuning and DPO provide a much better training resulting in models giving substantially better answers than models without this kind of finetuning as stated in literature [28], [37], [44], [54]. However, to unlock the full potential of MLMs, they would need even more **fine-grained feedback**. The longer the answers get, the less an aggregated score summarizing the human preference for the answer helps. Promising future directions are to analyze ways to target the feedback to certain parts of the answer. Consider multi-hop reasoning for example. Was the first step already faulty, or was it the final conclusion that did not fit to the previous intermediate results, although these were correct? This makes a big difference and would be problematic for humans as well, if we would always just get aggregated feedback. Imagine writing a two-page

essay and getting the grade as the only indicator on how well you performed. It would be very hard to get better at writing essays with this kind of feedback and no alternatives for learning. We need a similar development as it was performed for sentiment analysis when moving from an overall rating of a product review (positive/negative) to aspect-based sentiment analysis [55], that provides much finer grained judgements that are much more helpful. During the review process of this paper, OpenAI published own findings that support this claim [56].

Finally, **political correctness** and scientific problem solving seems to be overemphasised in recent models. None of the well performing models from December 2023 was willing to admit, that the likelihood of getting pregnant indeed has a causal relation to gender. Therefore, all models said that it is impossible to tell whether Gary or Mary are more likely to be pregnant. Also, several models insisted, that age is no solid basis for judging whether a 10-year-old or a 30-year-old person is more likely to work in a restaurant or school. For basic physics questions some of the new models performed bad because they went into too much detail and did not come to the point. This might be helpful in some benchmarks with no token limit and the only focus on final result but limits helpfulness for average users that get lost in the overly scientific explanations. Future models should better differentiate in those aspects. All results are published at opendata.iisys.de.

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